

**SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF ORGANIZING COOPERATION OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS
BODIES WITH CIVIL SOCIETY INSTITUTIONS****Mamadiev Ruziboy Utkirovich**Master's student at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of
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Abstract. In the article, based on the analysis of the practical activities of the internal affairs bodies, on the organization of the cooperation of crime prevention services with civil society institutions in the prevention of crimes and other offenses, as well as ensuring the rule of law, protecting the constitutional system, the rights, freedoms and legal interests of citizens, and the property of individuals and legal entities. scientifically based suggestions and recommendations are expressed.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, crime prevention services, civil society institutions, cooperation, organization of cooperation.

**ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ ОРГАНОВ
ВНУТРЕННИХ ДЕЛ С ИНСТИТУТАМИ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО ОБЩЕСТВА**

Аннотация. На основе анализа практической деятельности органов внутренних дел в статье рассмотрена организация взаимодействия правоохранительных органов с институтами гражданского общества в предупреждении преступлений и иных правонарушений, а также в обеспечении законности, защиты конституционного строя, прав, свобод и законных интересов граждан, имущества физических и юридических лиц. Высказаны научно обоснованные предложения и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: органы внутренних дел, службы профилактики правонарушений, институты гражданского общества, взаимодействие, организация взаимодействия.

INTRODUCTION

In the past short period, to identify and solve population problems, to introduce an effective cooperation system based on the principle of "neighborhood - sector - People's Reception - neighborhood", to practically ensure that the neighborhood is a reliable "bridge" between the people and the state, to support families and women. complex measures were implemented.

In recent times, significant measures have been taken to increase the role and importance of non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society in the implementation of democratic changes in all spheres of society and state life [1].

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In recent times, significant measures have been taken to increase the role and importance of non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society in the implementation of democratic changes in all spheres of society and state life, as well as social activity [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

By improving the structure of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, in order to introduce a unified system of managing and coordinating the activities of related civil society institutions, the

Cabinet of Ministers nominated "The best head of the regional internal affairs body", "The best preventive inspector", "The best investigator", "The best operative" The task of introducing the draft of the Government's decision on the holding of the annual republican competition for nominations was defined in the Presidential Decree № 6196 [3].

Through this, it was intended to further increase the efficiency of the internal affairs bodies, to further increase the intellectual knowledge and skills of the employees of the sector. The higher the knowledge and skills of the employee, the more he will fully understand his duties and perform them at a professional level.

Cooperation in the field of crime prevention - continuous analysis of the criminogenic situation in the administrative area, ensuring public order and citizens' safety, preventing crimes, improving the socio-psychological environment, neutralizing and eliminating criminogenic factors, according to behavior and lifestyle The law of all subjects on identifying persons prone to committing crimes and providing them with educational and preventive effects, solving committed crimes, identifying and apprehending wanted criminals, determining and eliminating the causes of crimes and the conditions that made them possible. and they work together in an agreed manner based on the powers, methods and forms specified in the legal documents [4].

As the Honorable President Sh.M.Mirziyoev noted, "The main goal of building an independent and strong state in Uzbekistan is to establish a fair society in which people, their rights and freedoms are of the highest value and are respected, as well as to ensure the rule of law, order, and the rights and freedoms of citizens in our society." necessary" [5].

In fact, ensuring the rule of law [6], strengthening the protection of the rights and interests of the individual, society and the state, increasing the legal consciousness and culture of the population, educating citizens in the spirit of obedience and respect for the law - this is not only the goal of building a developed, truly democratic legal state and a free civil society based on the market economy. its purpose, but also its means and factor, is the most important condition. Practice shows that in order to form legal consciousness and legal culture in the society, citizens have access to legal information, including the transparency of legal documents regulating human rights and freedoms, and defining the obligations of state bodies and officials to observe and protect these rights. , it is important that all conditions are created for their free use.

On February 9, 2017, the head of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoev [7] , gave a speech at the meeting dedicated to the activities of internal affairs bodies, existing problems and shortcomings in the system, and future tasks: elimination of deficiencies and problems in the activities of internal affairs bodies; identification of available opportunities and best practices for effective protection of the interests of the individual, society, and the state and their implementation; achieve effective implementation of measures to further democratize systemic management, ensure openness and transparency in the activities of its services and structural structures; the goal of ensuring the rule of law in society, that is, it requires carrying out fundamental reforms in the system of internal affairs bodies.

In particular, in May 2014, the adoption of the law "On the openness of the activities of state authorities and management bodies" was one of the necessary steps to further democratize public administration in our country, and to ensure the openness of the activities of state authorities and administration. According to it, it is guaranteed that the population, public associations and mass media will be widely informed about the activities of state authorities and management

bodies. Through the Law of our country "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities", extensive organizational and legal opportunities have been created to regulate the relations of individuals and legal entities to state bodies and institutions in the field of appeals. Also, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" in September 2016 has an extremely important place in the activities of internal affairs bodies[8].

RESULTS

Public opinion is also taken into account when planning the cooperation activities of prevention inspectors with civil society institutions. After all, "from the results of public opinion research at the stage of the entire republic: informing the population about the state of crime and effectively organizing legal propaganda; raising the reputation of internal affairs agencies among the population, creating a positive reputation of the police; formation and modification of the development concept of internal affairs agencies; in the development of social strategies related to the interaction of internal affairs agencies with the population; it can be used in the preparation of drafts of legal documents regulating the activities of law enforcement agencies, including internal affairs agencies"[9].

On the basis of the "Republic - region - district - neighborhood" system, the introduction of mechanisms of comprehensive management and continuous control, the effective coordination of the activities of internal affairs and other state bodies to ensure public safety, ensuring peace and stability in our country were defined as completely new mechanisms for organizing the activities of internal affairs bodies[10].

The work carried out did not meet the level demanded by the Honorable President, and it was first of all that the opportunities of local community activists, reconciliation commissions, well-respected people in the locality, and the general public were used on a wider scale.

On November 15, 2017, under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a result of the assignments and tasks given at the meeting of the video selector on the implementation of the tasks set in the prevention of crime and the fight against crime in our country, the existing problems and their solutions in this regard, the administration of sectors for the prevention of crime in the district territory, should be implemented in cooperation with law enforcement agencies and general public organizations measures have been defined and the responsibilities of prevention inspectors and other staff in crime prevention have been increased.

As can be seen from the above, preventive measures based on the slogan "There will be no crime in my neighborhood" are showing their effectiveness.

DISCUSSION

The practice of crime prevention shows that although a number of positive actions are currently being carried out in the field of internal departmental cooperation, as indicated above, there are still many problems that have not yet been resolved. In particular: cooperation of preventive services with other services in internal affairs agencies does not fully meet today's requirements; insufficient professional skills and legal knowledge of service employees participating in cooperation; lack of legal regulation of methods, forms and mechanism of interaction between services; that the responsibilities of all subjects involved in maintaining public order and ensuring security are not clearly defined in normative legal documents; the fact that preventive services are insufficiently provided with the equipment and means of communication

that meet the requirements of the time can be noted as factors that prevent the effective organization of cooperation of preventive services with other services of internal affairs agencies.

CONCLUSIONS

I think it is appropriate to implement measures:

first, to develop and put into practice the order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, which determines the organization of mutual cooperation between preventive inspectors and civil society institutions;

secondly, to develop and approve a model plan for organizing mutual cooperation between preventive inspectors and civil society institutions;

thirdly, defining cooperation between internal affairs bodies and civil society institutions as one of the most important tasks;

fourthly, to expand the authority of prevention inspectors in the organization of mutual cooperation of civil society institutions on the prevention of offenses in the administrative territory and clearly define it in relevant regulatory legal documents;

fifth, to establish a system of preparation and training of educational and practical manuals that regulate the cooperation of preventive inspectors with civil society institutions, the methods, forms and mechanisms of cooperation between them, as well as in the legal documents filled with the latest reforms;

sixth, to ensure the effective operation of the system of immediate delivery of information and data on crimes and their prevention between the services of internal affairs agencies;

seventh, to ensure the interest and responsibility of the parties for the results of the works carried out in mutual cooperation;

Eighthly, it will be appropriate to establish the use of digital technologies to ensure quick and effective communication of prevention inspectors with civil society institutions.

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